

Study of activation energy and order of reaction of some liquid crystals

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Liquid crystals of the type *p*-phenylene-di-*p*-*n*-alkoxy benzoate have been prepared. Kissinger isothermal decomposition method has been used for determination of activation energy values of liquid crystals. Kissinger's assessment for shape index of DTA peaks is used to find the order of reaction. There is no direct relationship between the carbon atoms in terminal methylene groups and E_a values. Order of reaction value decreases with increase in heating rate upto carbon atoms 10 in the terminal methylene group but beyond this the order increases or decreases.

Benzoate esters and benzoate derivatives are used as intermediates for liquid crystal preparation^{1,2}. Thermal stabilities of β -sistosteryl esters³ and thermal parameters of alkylcyanobiphenyl liquid crystals⁴ have been studied. Thermodynamic⁵ and thermochemical⁶ effects in cholesteric liquid crystals have been reported. The isobaric heat capacity, the phase transition temperatures and the enthalpy changes during transition have been studied for liquid crystals of *p*-acetylphenyl-*p*-*n*-hexyloxybenzoate and *p*-propoxyphenyl-*p*-*n*-hexyloxybenzoate⁷.

Literature survey reveals that some work on liquid crystals by laser study⁸, magnetic effect⁹, X-ray diffraction¹⁰ has been done, but no attention was directed towards the study of activation energy and order of reaction of the liquid crystals of the type *p*-phenylene-di-*p*-*n*-alkoxybenzoates. Hence, it was thought worthwhile to prepare the liquid crystals of the above type and study their activation energy and order of reaction.

Theoretical : In thermal analysis the amount of undecomposed reactants at a DTA peak temperature decreases with decrease in order of reaction (n). Therefore, the DTA peak becomes increasingly asymmetric as n is decreased (Fig. 1). The degree of asymmetry is called shape index (S) and can be calculated (Fig. 2). Shape index changes with change in order of reaction. From the theoretical plots of S vs n (Fig. 3) and S vs n^2 , (Fig. 4), it is clear that the second plot is linear ($S = 0.63 n^2$; hence, $n = 1.26 S^{1/2}$).

Results and Discussion

The peak temperature (T_m) was measured according to the reported procedure¹¹. Isothermal decomposition method¹² was used for calculation of activation energy (E_a) from the least-square equations of $\ln (\phi/T_m^2)$ vs $(1/T_m)$ for liquid crystals. The plots are not given but cast into $y = mx + c$ type equations given in Table 1.

Table 1. $\ln [\phi/(T_m^2)]$ vs $1/T_m$ plot equations based on the least-square method yielding E_a values

Mesophase*	Equation of st-line, where $A = \ln [\phi/(T_m)^2]$	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹
CH ₃ -bridge-C ₈ H ₁₇	$AT_m = -15000 + 36.4 T_m$	286.30
C ₂ H ₅ -bridge-C ₈ H ₁₇	$AT_m = -4000 + 0.85 T_m$	76.32
C ₃ H ₇ -bridge-C ₈ H ₁₇	$AT_m = -4000 + 1.60 T_m$	76.32
C ₄ H ₉ -bridge-C ₈ H ₁₇	$AT_m = -13750 + 29.72 T_m$	262.30
C ₅ H ₁₁ -bridge-C ₈ H ₁₇	$AT_m = -12500 + 26.10 T_m$	238.50
C ₆ H ₁₃ -bridge-C ₈ H ₁₇	$AT_m = -15000 + 33.10 T_m$	286.30
C ₈ H ₁₇ -bridge-C ₈ H ₁₇	$AT_m = -17500 + 40.25 T_m$	333.90
CH ₃ -bridge-C ₂ H ₅	(i) $AT_m = -3300 - 1.33 T_m$	62.96
	(ii) $AT_m = -14000 + 336.2 T_m$	2671.00
C ₂ H ₅ -bridge-C ₆ H ₁₃	(i) $AT_m = -6428.5 + 9.0426 T_m$	122.70
	(ii) $AT_m = -195000 + 528.5 T_m$	3720.00
C ₆ H ₁₃ -bridge-C ₇ H ₁₅	(i) $AT_m = -25000 + 68.30 T_m$	476.90
	(ii) $AT_m = -21666 + 50.76 T_m$	413.30

Fig. 1

Table 1 reveals that there is no direct relationship between the carbon atoms in terminal methylene groups and E_a values. It is evident that the changes are not orderly and may be due to (i) dipole-dipole interactions between the terminal chains and the bridging rings, (ii) parallel and antiparallel orientation of the terminal groups, (iii) sandwiching of the intermediate bridging groups and (iv) the relation between the nematic axis length and the molecular sizes of the nematogens due to parallel and antiparallel orientations. Substituents show their effect on mesomorphic properties¹³ but thermal characteristics of the mesophases are strongly dependent on the stereochemistry and structure of the molecules¹⁴.

$$\text{Shape Index } S = \frac{a}{b}$$

Fig. 2

It is observed that the E_a values for smectic to nematic transformations are very low as compared to nematic to isotropic liquid transformations, e.g. $\sim 63.0 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ for S-N and $\sim 2670.0 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ for N-I transition for CH_3 -bridge- C_2H_5 ; $\sim 123.0 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ for S-N and $\sim 3720.0 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ for N-I transition for C_2H_5 -bridge- C_6H_{13} . It may be due to planes of the phenyl rings being tilted so that more energy is required for N-I transitions. However, in S-N and N-I transitions vis-a-vis the alkyl chain (terminal) lengthening, the rotation of the plane or tilt of the bridging phenyl rings after some lapse of lengthening may again be such that they become co-planar and hence, it is expected that the E_a values for S-N and N-I would be nearly the same. This happens to be the observation in the present studies, e.g. C_6H_{13} -bridge- C_7H_{15} E_a for S-N change is $\sim 477.0 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and for N-I change is $\sim 413.0 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$.

Using Kissinger's¹⁵ assessment for shape index (S) of DTA-peaks (a and b values of Fig. 2), the order of reaction (n) was calculated (Table 2).

Fig. 3

Table 2. Order of reaction and shape index

n	n^2	S
0.4472	0.20	0.12
0.7071	0.50	0.30
1.0000	1.00	0.62
1.1180	1.25	0.78
1.2247	1.50	0.94
1.3228	1.75	1.10
1.4142	2.00	1.26
1.5000	2.25	1.40
1.6583	2.75	1.72
1.8027	3.25	2.04
1.9365	3.75	2.34
2.0000	4.00	2.52

The usual order of transition in the nematic phase transformation is ~ 1.0 but a careful observation shows that the order varies according to the heating rate (ϕ). In certain cases the order is ~ 2.0 (in the case of CH_3 -bridge- C_8H_{17} , C_2H_5 -bridge- C_8H_{17} , C_3H_7 -bridge- C_8H_{17} , C_6H_{13} -bridge- C_8H_{17} and CH_3 -bridge- C_6H_{13}).

The higher than one order observed is usually ascribed to pretransitional behaviour of the nematic mesophases. Another remote reason may be the heating rate changing from 1.25 to 10.0° per min, which imposes a sort of response functions and these functions diverge which is a clear signal for second order phase changes¹⁶. Landau and Lifshitz¹⁷ gave another mathematical explanation for pretransitional behaviour in nematics which is not observed in ordinary crystalline solids.

The values n (Table 3) show that the order of reaction decreases with increase in heating rate up to carbon atoms 10 in the terminal methylene groups with slight variations; beyond 10, the order increases or decreases. It is also seen that beyond carbon atoms 8 in the terminal methylene groups, the value of order of reaction decreases or in-

Fig. 4

creases successively in pairs of odd and even number of carbon atoms, i.e. 9,10; 11,12; 13,14 and 15,16. Another trend is also observed for odd and even number of carbon atoms beyond 8 in the terminal methylene groups. The value of order of reaction successively decreases or increases and so on for carbon atoms 9, 11, 13 and 15. The

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same trend is also observed for even number of carbon atoms in the terminal methylene groups : 10, 12, 14 and 16. This trend may be due to lengthening of molecular length and their different arrangements at the time of transition^{13,14}.

It is observed that the order of reaction changes with change in heating rate (ϕ). It may be due to continuous ordering and disordering of molecules in the crystals studied, as no decomposition is envisaged in these cases.

Table 3. Heating rates (ϕ), shape indices (S) and the order of reaction (n) from the shape index

Mesophase*	ϕ °C/min	S	$n =$ 1.26 $S^{1/2}$	Carbon atoms in terminal methylene groups
CH ₃ -bridge-C ₂ H ₅	1.25	0.9583	1.2334	3
	2.50	1.0769	1.3075	
	5.00	0.5555	0.9391	
	10.00	1.2000	1.3802	
CH ₃ -bridge-C ₃ H ₇	1.25	1.4285	1.5059	4
	2.50	0.3611	0.7571	
	5.00	0.9285	1.2141	
	10.00	0.4000	0.7969	
C ₂ H ₅ -bridge-C ₃ H ₇	1.25	0.9210	1.2092	5
	2.50	0.4918	0.8836	
	5.00	0.4400	0.8357	
	10.00	-	-	
CH ₃ -bridge-C ₅ H ₁₁	1.25	1.0000	1.2600	6
	2.50	0.4024	0.7992	
	5.00	1.3750	1.4774	
	10.00	0.2307	0.6051	
CH ₃ -bridge-C ₆ H ₁₃	1.25	3.7391	2.4364	7
	2.50	0.7727	1.1075	
	5.00	1.0000	1.2600	
	10.00	-	-	
CH ₃ -bridge-C ₇ H ₁₅	1.25	1.3953	1.4883	8
	2.50	0.2989	0.6888	
	5.00	0.5185	0.9072	
	10.00	0.3269	0.7204	
CH ₃ -bridge-C ₈ H ₁₇	1.25	2.3863	1.9464	9
	2.50	0.3962	0.7930	
	5.00	0.5116	0.9012	
	10.00	0.5000	0.8909	
C ₂ H ₅ -bridge-C ₈ H ₁₇	1.25	2.0000	1.7819	10
	2.50	1.2400	1.4030	
	5.00	1.1923	1.3758	
	10.00	0.3750	0.7715	
C ₃ H ₇ -bridge-C ₈ H ₁₇	1.25	0.5428	0.9283	11
	2.50	1.4230	1.5030	
	5.00	2.9375	2.1595	
	10.00	2.2857	1.9049	
C ₄ H ₉ -bridge-C ₈ H ₁₇	1.25	0.3392	0.7338	12
	2.50	0.5238	0.9119	
	5.00	0.7741	1.1085	
	10.00	1.3750	1.4774	
C ₅ H ₁₁ -bridge-C ₈ H ₁₇	1.25	0.8163	1.1384	13
	2.50	0.8333	1.1501	
	5.00	0.4800	0.8729	
	10.00	0.3684	0.7647	

Table-3 (contd.)

C ₆ H ₁₃ -bridge-C ₈ H ₁₇	1.25	1.0897	1.3152	14
	2.50	2.4047	1.9538	
	5.00	0.6511	1.0167	
	10.00	0.5000	0.8909	
C ₇ H ₁₅ -bridge-C ₈ H ₁₇	1.25	0.5833	0.9623	15
	2.50	1.2777	1.4242	
	5.00	0.9152	1.2053	
	10.00	1.3333	1.4549	
C ₈ H ₁₇ -bridge-C ₈ H ₁₇	1.25	0.3658	0.7620	16
	2.50	0.9531	1.2300	
	5.00	0.7812	1.1136	
	10.00	0.8000	1.1269	

*bridge : Same as in Table 1.

Experimental

p-Hydroxybenzoic acid (Koch light; 30 g) was mixed with ethanol (100 ml) and conc. sulphuric acid (3–5 ml). The mixture was refluxed to get *p*-hydroxyethyl benzoate. Potassium bromide (B.D.H.; 30 g) was treated with conc. sulphuric acid (25 ml) and the resulting hydrobromic acid was treated with *n*-alkyl alcohol (B.D.H.; 11 g) and conc. sulphuric acid (~15 ml) to get *n*-alkyl bromide. A mixture of sodium (S.M.; 6.5 g) in absolute alcohol (150 ml), *p*-hydroxyethyl benzoate (60 g) in absolute alcohol (140 ml) and *n*-alkyl bromide (40 g) was refluxed for 3 h to get *p*-alkoxyethyl benzoate as oily mass. A mixture of *p*-alkoxyethyl benzoate (50 ml) and 10% alcoholic KOH (B.D.H.; 250 ml) was refluxed and the mixture was acidified with conc. HCl. The solid obtained (*p*-alkoxybenzoic acid, 22 g) was treated with thionyl chloride (Robert Johnson; 37 g) to get *p*-*n*-alkoxybenzoyl chloride. The product thus obtained was mixed with saturated solution of hydroquinone (May & Baker; 0.5 mol) in dry pyridine (B.D.H.) to get *p*-hydroxyphenyl-*p*-*n*-alkoxybenzoate. The unsymmetrical esters, i.e. *p*-phenylene-di-*p*-*n*-alkoxy benzoates, were synthesized from the appropriate *p*-*n*-alkoxybenzoyl chlorides and *p*-hydroxyphenyl-*p*-*n*-alkoxybenzoates by essentially the same procedure as used in the preparation of the latter except that, at the start, a solution of the phenol was added to a solution of the acid chloride (3 moles for per mole of phenol) both in anhydrous pyridine medium.

The products were recrystallized from suitable solvents (dioxane, alcohol or hexane) and dried over silica gel in a desiccator. The elemental analyses were found satisfactory.

The DTG of the samples were taken on a MOM-Q-derivatorgraph at different heating rates.

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